

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Jones****FIRST NAME: Danine****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: Windows 10

THE TOOLS OF THE TRADE TO EXCELLENT WRITING

1)INTRODUCTION

For the average student, to write a good paper is fairly easy. The foundations of writing a good academic paper are usually established at the undergraduate level. One should have grasped the art of academic writing by the time one embarks on the journey to obtain a master's degree. However, to write an excellent paper is far more difficult. The student is required to comprehend a number of rules such as structuring sentences and paragraphs, avoiding plagiarism, referencing; including differing referencing styles and writing an effective conclusion, that would leave an indelible impression in the mind of the reader. An excellent essay should impress the reader so much that he or she is left with the desire to consume more than what has been written, whether by the same author or some other author regarding the same subject.

2)THE NEXT FOOD NETWORK STAR

The thesis statement should be compelling. The ACA-01A/ACA-401D Coursepack describes the thesis statement as “a possible answer to the question” or “point of view” (EUCLID 2019, 2). For me, these simple words were very helpful. When I hear the phrase “point of view”, I think of the “Food Network Show”: “Next Big Food Network Star”. Early in the life of the show, many contestants were sent home because the judges could not see a clear point of view from them. What was it that that particular contestant wanted to showcase with their cooking? This is a very simple analogy for what the thesis statement is.

It is often difficult to translate the thought, the idea, or the query into an actual thesis statement. I found this to be true when I embarked on my second masters. Since I did not have to do a thesis for my first masters, the process was very new to me and extremely daunting. I had all these questions floating around in my mind and I could articulate them when speaking to someone casually. However, when I arrived at the writing process, I drew a complete blank. I believe it was the first time in my entire academic career that I suffered from what published authors refer to as “writer’s block”.

After completing the first draft of the first chapter of the thesis both my supervisor as well as my aunt, who is a professor of law, questioned my thesis statement. They could not identify it. To my dismay, of course, as I thought that it was clearly articulated in the work that I had produced. However, it was not until I read the statement in the ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack, did I truly understand what a thesis statement should be. The thesis statement effectually provides a roadmap for both the author and the reader. The thesis should be like a journey into unexplored territory. Just like any journey is filled with excitement as one experiences the wonder of discovery, so too should an excellently written thesis be.

This roadmap should provide the reader with the tools to forge ahead in the journey that is set before him or her. As early as the introduction, the reader should be excited to discover what lies ahead; to see where the journey takes him or her. Once the roadmap provides a clear and distinctive path, the conclusion of the journey should not be bumpy or unexpected.

3) THE VALUE OF NOTE TAKING

Note taking is a tedious task. Sometimes it can be like stringing beads to make an intricately designed necklace. Wading through beads, crystals and jewels and choosing the pieces that will make a necklace worthy of being worn to a spectacular event is not an easy task. The work is tiring and boring at times but necessary to produce a good product. So, too, is the process of taking notes. The usefulness of note taking cannot be measured and it is folly to do research and not take the requisite notes as you discover more and more information about the area you are researching. It is like baking a cake without baking powder. The results often leave your essay flat as there is a tendency to omit information, which would have resulted in a better planned and well written essay: “It is important to take/make notes...always make notes with the question clearly in mind. You must use evidence to support your argument so look carefully for relevant information” (ibid).

Note taking makes referencing, building an argument, and defending your position an easier task than when no notes are taken. I have found that such tasks become an uphill battle when I neglect to take notes. I have often found myself in that position on several occasions. It is a trap cleverly designed by laziness, where the student believes that he or she can power through an essay simply relying on memory. It is amusing to think about and to remember several writing experiences where I failed to take notes and then I struggled to write my essay, to stay on track and to finish with a bang. The results were as expected. Sometimes in my haste to “just get it done”, I often think that it is far too time

consuming to take notes. What happens in fact, is that more time is taken wading through the mountain of material to find some bit of information that supports my point or contradicts my point. The lesson is a simple one: the writer cannot formulate a convincing argument that has the right flow, ebb, and cadence without having the information that is relevant to either prove or disprove his or her theory. When taking your notes, keep the thesis statement in mind. This is central to the task.

4) THE TWO-LEGGED STOOL

A two-legged stool cannot stand: (Williamson 1962). A simple phrase but very profound. Two legged stools cannot stand. They will most likely topple over, especially if you intend to put any weight on it. This is the perfect analogy for a one-sided argument. “Your essay should be balanced: that is, it should include a range of information and viewpoints from different authors that explore the key arguments and relevant aspects of a particular topic. [Do not] only include evidence that agrees with what you are arguing, if there are different or opposing views then they should be examined” (ibid). Perhaps it is human nature to wish to have no opposing view to your own. However, that would make for a very bland world if we all thought the same way. Interestingly, just today I read a legal opinion on the repatriation of seamen and the duty of cruise ship owners and the opinions contained in that paper were all different, so were the conclusions. This is in fact, the nature of life. We will not all agree.

Therefore, to write an essay citing sources that only support your viewpoint is without merit and foolhardy. The author cannot assuredly validate his or her argument without examining views contrary to his or her own. One should even go as far as examining a viewpoint that may dispel your argument entirely. This is what challenges the writer to produce a more compelling and convincing paper. The writer is given the ripe opportunity to immerse him or herself into deeper research and an avenue is created for greater analysis of the thesis question. The paper is enriched because of a more focused and profound analysis of the issues raised which, in turn, lends itself to a more balanced and reasoned argument and conclusion. Where the conclusion of the paper is to provide recommendations for change, it is found that such recommendations are far more robust.

Literature certainly benefits from this type of research. For example, for my last thesis, I conducted an examination of the United Nations (U.N.) Drug Conventions and their impact on small island developing states that wish to pursue trade in cannabis. Although this is a fairly new area of research, there were certainly several views shared in relation to the flexibility of the U.N. Drug Conventions. My opinion was that the purported flexibility was a mere façade that would impede rather than aid small island developing countries in their bid for economic development through trade in cannabis. Although my word limit restricted me from writing more than I wished to, I would like to believe that my view point and the citing of authors who disagreed with my analysis of the current situation would prompt more authors to examine this issue. As an academic, I believe that this should be one of your major aims, to spark a discussion that could lead to changes, even unexpected ones.

Where I was to simply write a thesis using information solely justifying my viewpoint, a deeper analysis of my writing may show that it has little or no merit. It would be like that two-legged stool that would topple over.

5) HOW MANY DRAFTS SHOULD I WRITE?

“Write the first draft to try out the structure and framework of your essay. A draft essay will help you work out how you will answer the question and which evidence and examples you will use and how your argument will be structured” (EUCLID 2019, 3). This recommendation was hard for me to swallow. Having pursued my academic career long distance since 2012, I know it is demanding. Unlike going on campus, where my only focus was school, long distance studying is accompanied by other commitments such as work and home responsibilities. I have often found myself in a position where my first draft is my only version. The race against time is a constant battle for the long- distance student.

That being said, the recommendation is not only sound, but endorsed. In practical terms, the benefit of having several drafts of an essay cannot be underestimated. For example, in legislative drafting, one must do several drafts of a piece of legislation, whether that requirement is self-imposed, or client driven. In the end it makes for a better piece of drafting. Essay writing is remarkably similar in nature. As Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma posit, you produce a better essay when you do more than one draft. There have been many occasions where I have submitted my first and only draft and as I am reading it over in my quiet time, I am aghast by what I have submitted. I discover areas that required improvement and the results spoke for themselves.

Producing several drafts also helps a student become more disciplined and more mindful of time management. You must prioritise your time to do your research, take your notes and collate your resources so that you set aside the time to embark on the drafting process.

6) PLAGIARISM- THE THIEF OF WORDS, THOUGHTS AND IDEAS

Plagiarism is well understood by any academic writer. Once you embark on an academic career, you will encounter this word and the concept of plagiarism and you are required to understand it and its consequences. I was once asked to be part of a legislative drafting consortium, examining legislation of a particular Caribbean country. My task was to draft the report. I was told that I could simply look at similar reports and switch around the words. No big deal. I was told. When I questioned the approach, the answer was that I was too much of an academic, that I could not fit into the real world of practicing law. What an eye opener for me. The questions are: “Why should anyone bother mentioning the source of where information came from? What [is] the harm?” (EUCLID 2019, 5). The answers are “Plagiarism is wrong and unethical. It is not fair to take someone’s work and

not give them credit [and] it is a serious academic offence and can have serious consequences” (ibid).

To achieve academic excellence, plagiarism, in any form must be avoided at all cost. How can a student claim that he or she contributed to the literature of a particular field or a new perspective to a particular area, if the work does not belong to him or her? Plagiarism is academic suicide. In some cases, it results in expulsion from a programme, which is the ultimate penalty for such an infraction. In my opinion, I agree wholeheartedly that plagiarism is an affront to ethical and moral values (ibid). I am a firm advocate of intellectual property and giving full credit to the creator of works in whatever form. It is rather unfortunate that some hold the view that all you should do is use a thesaurus and substitute words with others in an attempt to hide what is the obvious, that you are trying to pass work off someone else’s work as your own.

Proper referencing is the key to ensure that plagiarism is avoided. In-text citations, paraphrasing, direct quotations, end and foot notes and referencing through a bibliography are some of the tools of proper referencing that Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma explain in the Coursepack (EUCLID 2019, 6-13). One aspect of plagiarism that was not discussed however, that I would have been interested to hear views about, is the aspect of self-plagiarism. This was a concept I was first introduced to when I embarked on my second master’s degree. The University of South Wales in its introductory course for its students admonishes students not to copy their own work without giving credit to the source of the work: me. Josh Blackman notes: “Within legal academia, “little consensus” exists about the ethicality of self-plagiarism”. Contributing to this uncertainty is, perhaps, the inescapable fact that so much of the legal work product is deliberately repetitive”. (Blackman, Volume 45:3, 644). Indeed, it is quite tempting to cut and paste previous work, especially if it is the same topic that is being discussed and it was your work to begin with.

Since Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma did not discuss it in the Coursepack, for me it remains to be seen whether or not it is in fact an acceptable form of writing or if it is a mark of disrespect to oneself. (OSCOLA Referencing Guide 2014, 3).

7) CONCLUSION

The PHD experience is one that appears to be daunting. In fact, I have had a few persons tell me not to travel the path as it is way too demanding and there are times you will hit a bump that you would not be able to or do not have the strength to navigate. However, all journeys have their bumps. It is the fortitude and character of the traveler that will show whether the journey is worth taking. This is my uncharted territory and there may be many bumps ahead. However, the Coursepack has provided me with invaluable information that I require to assist me along the way. Like “Dora the Explorer”, I must put these tools in my backpack and be ready to take them out when they are necessary. I must first remember they are there, and I must use them in the intended manner, in order to make this journey a success.

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